

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

Milestone 11: Dedicated project space for DT4H available at the OpenEBench benchmarking platform

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Version Log

Issue Date	Version	Involved	Comments
29/09/2025	0.1	Carles Hernandez-Ferrer	Initial version
30/09/2025	0.2	Laia Codó, Josep Lluís Gelpí	Second version
30/09/2025	Final	Cristian Izquierdo, Xènia Puig, Karim Lekadir	Revised and corrected final version

Executive Summary

This milestone (MS11) reports the availability of a dedicated project space for DataTools4Heart (DT4H) within the ELIXIR OpenEBench benchmarking platform. The DT4H benchmarking hub will systematically integrate benchmarking efforts undertaken across the project on tools, scientific outcomes, user experience, software quality, and overall performance. It provides a centralised and FAIR-compliant environment for transparent, reproducible, and community-driven benchmarking of DT4H toolbox components (e.g., NLP models, federated learning algorithms, synthetic datasets).

Table of Contents

Version Log	2
Executive Summary	2
Acronyms	3
List of tables	3
List of figures	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Benchmarking in DT4H	4
3 Infrastructure	5
3.1 DT4H @ OpenEBench	5
4 Future Work	6

Acronyms

OEB: OpenEBench

FL: Federated Learning

NLP: Natural Language Processing

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible

List of tables

[Table 1: Overview of XXXX \(example table caption\). 4](#)

List of figures

[Figure 1: Illustration of XXXX \(example figure caption\) 5](#)

1 Introduction

This document outlines the technical capabilities and operational framework of the benchmarking platform designed as part of the DataTools4Heart (DT4H) European project. It serves as a centralised hub for recording a technical summary of project’s benchmarking decisions, goals, agreements, and capabilities. Crucially, will provide the structured space to:

- List the datasets used for benchmarking (including references to the DT4H’s data catalogue).
- Detail the complete roster of benchmarked assets.
- Comprehensive description and results for all benchmarking events.

Along the task, the benchmarking hub will be populated by a series of benchmarking efforts performed within the DT4H project frame. The overarching goal is to elucidate the right tool for the right scenario by enabling consistent, objective evaluation across different technical areas. This consistency is critical for advancing the state-of-the-art in heart disease data processing and analysis.

2 Benchmarking in DT4H

Benchmarking in DT4H is transversal, covering scientific outcomes, user experience, software quality, and the overall performance of the platform. Assets to be evaluated include:

- baseline NLP tools and transformer-based AI models,
- federated learning models trained under novel schemas (e.g. centre dropout, unbiased aggregation methods)
- synthetic cardiology dataset (CardioSyn)

Such benchmarking efforts are carried out by the relevant WPs (see [Table 1. Benchmarking-related tasks](#)) and later integrated as structured evaluations into the DT4H OpenEBench portal, ensuring transparent comparison and long-term availability of results.

Table 1. Benchmarking-related tasks

T6.4	Development of an evaluation environment for DT4H toolbox
T3.6	Integration of clinical NLP models into federated learning framework
T4.2	Centre dropout for efficient federated learning
T5.4	Technical Evaluation of Synthetic Data Sets for Cardiology
T4.3	Unbiased aggregation in federated learning
T7.4	Multi-centre evaluation and feedback loop

Of these, T6.4 is responsible for linking DT4H with OpenEBench and adapting the platform to fit the benchmarking approach followed by each of the other tasks.

3 Infrastructure

The main achievement introduced in this milestone is the DT4H benchmarking platform built upon the existing infrastructure of OpenEBench.

OpenEBench is the **ELIXIR Benchmarking and Technical Monitoring platform**. It is a publicly available, community-driven platform designed to centralise and standardise the results of technical assessments, validations, and benchmarks for bioinformatics tools and workflows. Its core capabilities include:

- **Standardisation:** Providing standardised metrics, methods, and reporting schemas for tool evaluation.
- **Centralisation:** Acting as a repository for benchmarking results across diverse domains.
- **Reproducibility:** Facilitating the creation of reproducible benchmarking events, or *challenges*.
- **Community Engagement:** Allowing different scientific teams to compare their tools and methods fairly in a transparent environment.

OpenEBench provides the necessary framework and technical specifications to ensure DT4H's benchmarking efforts are transparent, consistent, and comparable with wider European life science initiatives.

3.1 DT4H @ OpenEBench

DT4H has been integrated at OpenEBench as a new dedicated project space (see [Figure 1. DataTools4Heart space at OpenEBench](#)). Accessible at the OpenEBench portal (*Home* <https://openebench.bsc.es/> → *Projects* → *Datatools4Heart card*), it will integrate a comprehensive view of DT4H assessment areas, produced metrics, computation pipelines and quality indicators. Participating WPs will contribute evaluation outputs to this space, ensuring harmonisation across the consortium.

DataTools4Heart project space	https://openebench.bsc.es/projects/OEBC014
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Furthermore, this section of the platform acts as a centralised hub of links to external tools, data sources, and other platforms that have been used to benchmark and compare tools, ensuring users have a single point of reference for all related technical documentation.

The screenshot shows the OpenEBench interface for the DataTools4Heart project. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'BENCHMARKING', 'PROJECTS', 'TOOLS', 'OBSERVATORY', 'DOCS', and 'ABOUT' tabs, along with a 'LOGIN' button. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home > Project Spaces > DataTools4Heart'. The main heading is 'DataTools4Heart' with a subtitle 'European Health Data Toolbox for Cardiology Data'. A paragraph describes the project's goal: building an innovative, federated, privacy-preserving cardiology data platform. A 'DataTools4Heart' logo is shown. Keywords include 'federated learning; data privacy; synthetic data; cardiology; multilingual Natural Language Processing (NLP); AI modelling;'. A link to the 'MainSite' is provided. On the left, a sidebar menu lists 'Summary', 'Results', 'Datasets', and 'Tools'. The main content area features a large heading 'DataTools4Heart' followed by a bulleted table of contents: '0. Executive Summary', '1. Introduction', '2. Assessment Areas' (with sub-items: '2.1. Platform User Experience', '2.2. AI Toolbox Models', '2.3. AI Clinical Datasets', '2.4. AI Synthetic Datasets', '2.5. NLP Models Evaluation'). Below this is the '0. Executive Summary' section, which repeats the project's mission statement.

Figure 1. DataTools4Heart space at OpenEBench

4 Future Work

While the benchmarking platform is already operational, the current version contains only the skeleton of the future hub. Next steps include keep working in collaboration with the rest of the *Benchmarking Working Group* for completing the list of evaluable toolbox components (datasets, models, tools) and both:

- Organising continuous evaluation and feedback loops (multi-centre, user-driven)
- Preparing thematic benchmarking events (e.g., NLP model evaluation, federated learning robustness, synthetic data validation)

The result of this effort would be a centralised benchmarking hub for DT4H tools, organised by thematic area (benchmarking event) and task (challenge). Every benchmarking-related task of the DT4H project is to collect and submit its outcome to populate the **centralised DT4H space in OpenEBench**. Currently, most of these tasks are under progress.